

The Incorporation of Near Real Time Ionospheric Propagation Information for Automated Link Establishment Based Communication Systems

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1. INTRODUCTION

This paper focuses on the use of the HF frequency band, 3-30 MHz, as a wireless communications medium where the predominant propagation mode is provided by ionospheric refraction. The HF medium provides a reliable mode of long distance, beyond line of sight communications used by many nations and entities worldwide.

The paper begins with an overview of existing automated link establishment (ALE) systems which provide a mechanism to find the best propagating frequency between radios located anywhere on Earth and to set up the radios for communication. The paper will provide a brief history of ALE throughout the years up to and including the most recent US MIL-STD-188-141D.

Next, the use of propagation prediction software is discussed with a concentration on VOACAP. This package provides a prediction of the best propagating frequency between points on Earth based on many factors including geographic positions, time of day, solar activity, and noise conditions. VOACAP is generally used to select possible / probable frequencies to use before radios are deployed in the field but does not have a mechanism to address real time variations in propagation.

Sources of Near Real Time (NRT) propagation information are then discussed. This information includes WWV broadcasted geomagnetic and solar indices information, inputs from space weather organizations, and amateur radio propagation probing waveforms such as WSPR.

A comparison of various waveforms for real time channel evaluation is then presented. Waveforms used by the US MIL-STD ALEs, WSPR and previous experiments are examined.

A Machine Learning (ML)-based consolidation model combining the above information is then presented including comparison of the model to both VOACAP predictions and real world measured propagation measurements.

Finally, an enhanced ALE based system is presented, based on the latest MIL-STD, combined with all the previously discussed NRT information- and ML-based models. The best approach to experimentally validating this system is discussed and the potential way forward is outlined.

2. CURRENT STATE OF AUTOMATIC LINK ESTABLISHMENT

The concept of ALE was borne out of the common operational requirement of HF communication networks to be ready to transmit traffic at any moment. Before ALE, highly

skilled, dedicated operators manually assessed propagation conditions on each of their links, continually maintaining the network. With the advent and advancement of microcontroller-based radio systems and complex signal processing algorithms, fully automatic assessment, maintenance, and link establishment became possible and are commonplace today.

ALE systems have been developed since the early 1980's with even the earliest systems still seeing use throughout the world by a wide range of user communities [Batts, *et al.*, 2019]. Standardized ALE protocols are commonly referred to by their "generation," much in the same way as cellular telephone standards, despite having no relation. ALE systems commonly define station addressing schemes and over-the-air protocol data units, the combination of which are used to perform the operations of the system, e.g., establishing links, as obviously implied by its name. Though as human operators before the invention of ALE, these systems can perform link assessment on a regular basis, autonomously identifying the best channels to use at any given time.

1st generation (1G) ALE is represented by proprietary systems of various manufacturers, which were not interoperable due to their independent development. However, these systems showcased the possibilities of ALE, leading to great interest in the development of an interoperable standard. The result of this effort was US Fed-STD 1045 and US MIL-STD-188-141A, commonly referred to as 2G ALE [US MIL-STD-188-141A, 1990]. These standards utilized the best concepts from the 1G implementations, defining a collection of capabilities now considered mandatory for any ALE system. 2G's identifying features are an 8-ary FSK physical layer modem and asynchronous scanning operation. 2G continues to be widely employed with great success by a vast array of HF users, owing in part to both its fundamental simplicity as well as support for highly complex networks.

NATO STANAG 4538 defines an ALE system commonly referred to as 3G ALE [STANAG 4538, 2000]. 3G was designed to incorporate the latest developments in HF physical waveforms, digital signal processing (DSP) capabilities and other technological advancements such as GPS. 3G's identifying features are a serial-tone burst waveform and synchronous scanning operation. 3G improved on the performance aspects of ALE systems, operating at lower SNRs, and establishing links faster than 2G, on average, while supporting many of its capabilities and all core link maintenance functions.

Both 2G and 3G natively support only 3 kHz traffic channels and data waveforms with the traffic's bandwidth and center frequency being implicitly related to the ALE waveforms. With the advent of wider-than-3 kHz, bandwidth-agile HF data waveforms, an ALE system with the ability to both establish a link on a channel and negotiate a traffic bandwidth and center frequency became necessary. L3Harris extended 3G to support wideband HF with a secondary burst handshake to perform the wideband channel negotiation after the link was established by the pre-existing 3G ALE handshake. This extension, named 3GWB, allowed simultaneous 3G network support for both 3 kHz-only and newer wideband HF-capable equipment [Furman, *et al.*, 2016].

Most recently, the standard specifying 2G was updated to US MIL-STD-188-141D and now defines 4G ALE, a natively wideband-capable protocol [US MIL-STD-188-141D, 2017]. As HF networks are expected to support more diverse user traffic types, some with sensitivity to latency, such as IP, an ALE that can quickly establish a wideband HF link became necessary. 4G

builds on the decades of experience from 1G, 2G and 3G protocols; as 2G took the best ideas from the multiple 1G implementations, 4G integrates concepts from both 2G and 3G and defines an ALE which can be simple, fast, and robust, while still supporting highly complex networks. Like 3G, 4G utilizes serial-tone burst waveforms, though defines two different types, one for fast linking on good channels and one for linking on challenged channels, allowing for the robust performance expectation set by 3G while supporting faster linking when conditions allow. 4G supports both asynchronous and synchronous scanning as well as staring ALE, simultaneously receiving multiple channels by sufficiently capable equipment, providing for flexibility to best accommodate a network's specific needs. As 2G and 3G have supported successful use of the HF medium for many decades, 4G is poised to do the same for the era of wideband HF.

3. THE ROLE OF PROPAGATION PREDICTION PROGRAMS

As a companion to ALE, HF Propagation Prediction tools are often used to develop a frequency plan for an upcoming mission. Several prediction tools are available, including the highly regarded Voice of America Coverage Analysis Program (VOACAP), courtesy of NTIA/ITS. Developed for Voice of America (VOA), based on Ionospheric Communications Analysis and Prediction Program (IONCAP), and originally designed by the National Bureau of Standards (NBS) Boulder, it has been widely used and trusted for many decades to estimate the best HF frequency to use at a given time.

This package provides a prediction of the best propagating frequency between points on Earth based on many factors including geographic positions, time of day, solar activity, and noise conditions. VOACAP is generally used to select possible / probable frequencies to use before radios are deployed in the field but does not have a mechanism to address real time variations in propagation.

4. SOURCES OF NEAR REAL-TIME PROPAGATION INFORMATION

Beyond monthly median SNR predictions, it might be useful in some circumstances to take advantage of any NRT information that is available [Buckley, *et al.*, 2021].

Radio station WWV has been a useful source of real-time propagation information for several decades, with hourly observations and forecasts of solar flux, planetary A, planetary K, and space weather indices. This information is made available over-the-air to HF radio operators via in-band spoken descriptions as part of WWV's products, without any need for internet connectivity. This information can be heard by the operator for their use; alternately, speech-to-text methods can utilize the forecasts for propagation prediction.

The Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC) (<https://www.swpc.noaa.gov>) maintains a wealth of information of both historical observations and forecasts of solar flux, planetary K and planetary A indices, geomagnetic storm ("G") levels, solar radiation storm ("S") levels and radio blackout ("R") levels. As above, this information can be used by operators, or alternately the forecast can be used to predict propagation in near real-time.

The Weak Signal Propagation Reporter (WSPR) (<https://www.wsprnet.org/>) sends and receives low-power transmissions to test propagation on the MF and HF bands, for the purpose of probing potential communication paths. Transmitters signal their callsign, Maidenhead grid locator, and transmitter power in dBm. Receivers generate a spot report consisting of this decoded information along with the call sign, location and received SNR at the receive site. WSPR provides this data in near real-time and can be used for both training data for machine learning models, as well as recent link performance.

Several other sources of similar information exist, including the German Research Centre for Geosciences (<https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/>), which maintains a useful history of planetary K and other relevant information.

5. IMPROVED CHANNEL EVALUATION WAVEFORMS

Recent experiments with a “Doppler and Multipath Sounding Network” (DAMSON) used several sounding waveforms to measure Doppler and Multipath, including a) a Barker-13 pulse sequence at 2400 symbols per second (1.6 seconds long); b) A passive noise measurement (2.8 seconds); and c) CW (4.3 seconds). This was used to characterize challenging high latitude links, and the results drove the performance requirements of STANAG 4415.

Several ALE waveforms are in use, with a variety of capabilities: a) 2G (supports 3 kHz waveforms); b) 3G (supports 3 kHz natively, 3GWB supports up to 24 kHz waveforms); c) 4G (supports up to 48 kHz bandwidth waveforms).

Recent advances permit noise and interference monitoring as well, enabled in part by the more prevalent use of direct sampling (DS) receivers. Many such receivers are available, including the Perseus receiver (covering 1 MHz up to full HF band); the Kiwi SDR receiver (used as a network of receivers spread across the world and accessible to most users, includes WSPR spots and database); multi-channel receivers and Staring ALE.

6. A MACHINE LEARNING BASED CONSOLIDATION MODEL

A set of ML-based models were created that trains on a consolidated set of observations from VOACAP, WSPR and SWPC, for the use of then making inferences (predictions) based on near real-time forecasts from WWV, SWPC and potentially elsewhere.

The first model was created for the month of March of 2020, a relatively quiet period of time that was low in the sunspot cycle. The WSPR data remains consistent over these three days, from an ML perspective, matching the model to the WSPR data was quite straightforward, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. WSPR Training Data vs. WSPR-based ML Model Comparison

The active month of March 2015 was modeled, with a NOAA SWPC report from the week of March 16-22, 2015, indicating high Kp values from March 17 and beyond, associated with the arrival of a coronal mass ejection (CME) on March 15 [Chernigovskaya, M. A. et al., (2020)]. March 18 is notable, where the number of WSPR reports dropped dramatically, and indicated relatively poor communications on that day [Furman, et al., 2022]. Figure 2 indicates that the ML model tracks the significant day-to-day changes quite well.

Figure 2. WSPR-based ML Model Predictions vs WSPR data, selected days from March 2015

The true usefulness of such an ML model would be to accurately predict future conditions. To that end, a model of the month of August from 2015 through 2021 was trained, and then used to make predictions for August of 2022. Figure 3 shows excellent agreement (low RMS error) between the ML inference and the actual WSPR data for that month.

Figure 3. WSPR-based ML Model Predictions vs WSPR data, August 2022

Active days (for example, August 8) had respectable performance but higher RMS error. Investigations and ideas for further improvement are presently underway, including data science explorations of the imbalanced data sets (many more quiet days than active, sparse reporting during rising and falling propagation conditions), handling of outliers in the training data, and the overall veracity of the WSPR training data itself.

7. AN ENHANCED ALE-BASED SYSTEM

Figure 4 shows how the ALE-based system would incorporate an ML feature. The ALE result (currently 4G) would likely always provide the best information, especially if it was recently acquired. The ML inference could be added as a weighted “vote”, that may be useful when the ALE information is stale or otherwise unavailable. The ML vote is optionally modified to account for local effects for a particular Tx EIRP and Rx station impairments. Similarly, VOACAP can be added into the system for coarse propagation guidance, as desired.

Figure 4. Enhanced ALE-based System Block Diagram

8. TESTING POTENTIAL SYSTEM IMPROVEMENTS

L3Harris regularly participates in internal and external test exercises, including ALE testing and propagation planning. A future controlled-environment test is envisioned, where both VOACAP and ML predictions would be compared to fresh and stale ALE measurement and WSPR reports, to determine the best use of each feature in a comprehensive system.

It is anticipated that a fresh ALE reading would provide the best results, with VOACAP providing a solid backup prediction and ML potentially providing improved NRT predictions.

9. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Current ALE measurement continues as the optimum means of determining the best frequency to use between HF radios at a given time. When ALE information is stale or otherwise unavailable, VOACAP is a trusted means of predicting the best frequency. ML techniques show promise of predicting the best frequency to use under near real-time conditions, during both quiet and active periods.

Formal field-testing campaigns under real-world conditions are envisioned, to compare ALE vs. VOACAP vs. ML results. The L3Harris team will continue to explore additional sources of both observed and predicted propagation data; run tests with known local noise and interference conditions; optimize the training database for handling outliers and imbalanced datasets and continue to explore new ML models.

REFERENCES

- Batts, W., Nieto, J., & Furman, W. (2019). A Comparison of Automated Link Establishment Techniques for Wideband HF. Proceedings of the Nordic Shortwave Conference, Nordic HF19
- MIL-STD-188-110A (1990). "Military Standard - Interoperability and Performance Standards for Data Modems", Draft US Dept of Defense
- STANAG 4538 (2000). "Technical Specifications To Ensure Interoperability Of An Automatic Radio Control System For HF Communication Links", Edition 1, North Atlantic Treaty Organization
- Furman, W., Nieto, J., & Batts, W. (2016). On Air Operation of the Harris Adaptive Wideband Cognitive ALE. Proceedings of the Nordic Shortwave Conference, Nordic HF16
- MIL-STD-188-141D (2017) "Interoperability and Performance Standards for Medium and High Frequency Radio Systems", US Dept of Defense
- Buckley, Richard J. and Furman, William N. (2021). Application of Machine Learning Techniques to HF Propagation Prediction, MILCOM 2021 - 2021 IEEE Military Communications Conference, ISBN978-1-6654-3972-5.

Chernigovskaya, M. A. et al. (2020). Longitudinal variations of geomagnetic and ionospheric parameters in the Northern Hemisphere during magnetic storms according to multi-instrument observations. *Advances in Space Research*.

Furman, William N., Buckley, Richard J. and Seeber, Ryan (2022). Application of Machine Learning Techniques to HF Propagation Prediction and Deployment Considerations in Tactical HF Radios, *Proceedings of the Nordic Shortwave Conference*.